

The State of Trans Gender's A Case of District Rawalpindi

Author Details:

Rohma Shafqat-M.Phil. Scholar, Institute of Social and Cultural Studies, Quaid Azam Campus, University of the Punjab, Lahore, Pakistan

Abstract

This research paper identifies and describes the state of transgender and how they are surviving in this society. In this world, Pakistan is the second largest Islamic state. Islam has given equal rights to everyone. Through electronic and print media, we found that being an Islamic state; still transgender is neglected by the government and the local society. In general, they are usually associated with dancing, prostitution, and begging. To identify the state of transgender's in district Rawalpindi, a quantitative and qualitative survey has been conducted. A sample of 60 respondents was taken in district Rawalpindi. To dig the hole deeper, existing literature on the topics was thoroughly reviewed. The questionnaire was prepared in the light of research objectives for data collection. Suitability of the questionnaire was examined through its pretesting on the ten respondents. Interviewing with questionnaire schedule was used as a tool to collect data. Finally, through SPSS (statically package for social sciences) was used for data analysis.

Keywords: trans genders, violence, human rights, laws, sociology, Rawalpindi

INTRODUCTION

The term transgender is used for people whose gender identity, expression or behavior is different from those typically associated with their assigned sex at birth.

Beyond doubt, transgender community in Pakistan has faced multiple levels of societal discrimination, and institutional. Though, the Constitution of Pakistan protects all citizens by safeguarding their rights, status and dignity; these rights are not translated into laws and protection mechanisms at the state level with respect to vulnerable groups and specifically the transgender community.

In general, if we discuss their early age, they face social discrimination from the family level. They are considered less accomplished or significant as likened to their rest of the children, family disregards them and pay no noteworthy consideration. There is no exact number of populations of transgender available living in Pakistan leading by two reasons; first there has been no census after 1998, two, even in that last national census transgender were not recognized as third gender officially and therefore all data was marked in male sex boxes. Different study and survey reports share the approximate number of transgender 0.4 million, however some quote, 1.5 million and some quote 0.5 million.

Maliciously, Transgender individuals in Pakistan have typically faced a myriad of dangers from family, community, police, and religious authorities, and had to leave the country. Losing the family safety net means losing much of societal rights and protection. They become an easy quarry of different abuse i.e. sexual abuse and physical assault goes through social-psycho shock and having the feelings of refusal.

Ideally, Transgender peoples form around guru-chela relations, alike to the master-disciple relationships of Sufism, providing a source of guard and support for persons cast out by their families. While guru-chela groups retain their reputation to this day, there is also a cumulative number of persons who have accepted a worldwide transgender individuality external these old-style organizations. Irrespective of whether they become chelas, many transgender Pakistanis are also trying to uphold relations with their family and relatives. Though, increasing familial acceptance has brought its own set of challenges, mainly in the realm of inheritance. In Pakistan, inheritance portions are often strongminded by gender, with women receiving half the amount of men. According to this scenario Al Jazeera stated that one of the senator informed them, transgender persons will receive an inheritance based on the gender identity they have transitioned into and chosen for themselves. "Transgenders have the equal right to live with self-respect and avail all fundamental and essential rights certain by the constitution.

In the current century, transgenders are struggling to get their fundamental rights such as the Right to health, education, politics. Majority of the transgender people do not get a chance to follow education in regular schools. Outrageously, in admission forms, there are only two gender options: Male and Female. But In 2012, the Supreme Court of Pakistan granted transgenders a place on the National Identity Cards and pronounced their inalienable right to

get education but no provincial government has so far succeeded in implementing this decision. Further in the same vein, they are facing multiple discrimination like harassment and violence simply on the basis of their gender and identity. Despite Supreme Court of Pakistan's ruling in 2009 that 'transgender be given equal inheritance and job opportunity rights, amongst others'; no proactive action has been undertaken to this end.

Despite the horrible state of transgenders, however, the Transgender Persons (Protection of Rights) Bill, 2017, comprises measures such as official recognition of an individual's identity as they observe it, and protection from discrimination and harassment. In the same vein, Pakistan's parliament also has approved a law guaranteeing basic rights for transgender people in a country which sees prevalent this discrimination. In the fever of transgenders another this protection of rights bill was successfully passed by the majority of the members of national assembly. The law bans discrimination in contradiction of transgender people by business owners and employers also illegalization harassment in public places or they are living. This law also allows transgender people to self-identify as male, female or a "third sex" on official documents, such as passports or driver's licenses. Pakistan also passes Landmark Transgender Rights Law, the new law bars discrimination against hiring transgender employees and also guarantees basic human rights for them. Called "Transgender Persons (Protection of Rights) Act", the legislation was passed on in Islamabad. With this, all citizens will have the right to identify as male, female, a mix of both genders or neither, on national identity cards, driver's license, passport and education certificates/degrees. It defines gender identity as "a person's innermost and individual sense of self as male, female or a blend of both, or neither; that can correspond or not to the sex assigned at birth".

Notwithstanding a series of watertight legal protections including the recent amendment to a 2017 transgender protection bill stating a medical test is not obligatory to identify one's gender the community's reality calls for urgent action. Reflect the surge of attacks on transgender women in recent years, and the police's failure to respond. The impoverished state of transgenders serves as an accusation of the state's disgraceful indifference when it comes to preservative the basic rights of such susceptible groups with bare recourse to opportunity and justice.

Logically speaking, the Constitution should have been adequate to assurance transgenders the rights settled to each and every Pakistani. Not so in this cultural milieu, though, where gender controls much of how an individual's life plays out, and what society owes to him/her. In such a setting, transgenders are by meaning at a difficulty. Paradoxically, not so long ago, eunuchs or transsexuals a term that falls under the transgender umbrella liked a raised status in the royal courts of undivided India. Over time though, in a painful overturn of fate, they were abridged to a worthless being, pandering to the talismans of society that desensitized and preserved them with disdain. There have been a number of instances of terrible abuse against them, of rape, battery and other kinds of violence met with unimportance or even mockery by those in a situation to help. The anticipated legislation on the anvil is, so, unhappily sufficient, much needed. But, as honor killings demonstrate, the law is inadequate in itself to eliminate society issues or change individual behaviors. It is proposed that, state and society both have to be active in bringing transgenders into the mainstream through opportunities in education and employment.

Sociological and psychological problems (Broader prospective)

It is really mockeries when someone asked who am i? This question was asked me many times by so called humans in the world. This question really hurt me, how, why, I am like this. Still my identity is not recognized in lot of countries. Due to of societal, economical, barriers I cannot get good job at government and as well as private sector. Recently, incident in Peshawar, when an innocent transgender person, Nazo, was shot dead at her flat and later the body was chopped to pieces, are we humans too, are we free in this world? Or we have any Right to live in this world?

In the same vein, due to of some unique type of nature, most of them hesitate to drink, eat, and shake hands with them. This type of cruel discrimination leaves thousand questions in our minds. Although, they are citizen of this country and are free in their actions to live their life. But in traditional society like Pakistan, they are living marginalized. Malevolently, living life without job, they are struggling to earn safe money. In the early life, loss of families led their life more miserable. They live with so-called safe heaven community for transgender. More or less Illiteracy, lack of knowledge, make their life more miserable. Beside this, educated English speaking class of eunuch is enlarging in Pakistan. They do not face this action because of their social and economic position in the society. They become fashion designers, interior decorators, hair stylists' etc. It is factual that human psychology is a wounded to the supremacy of heterosexual society contrived by culture and society. But it is also ironic to blame whole society wrong in its demeanor against transgenders. They have their part in fabricating this approach toward themselves. A maximum number of transgenders are turning to prostitution, which goes against the transgender ideal of asceticism.

Objective of the research:

The main objectives of the study are to identify the state of transgender's people who face different problems living in Rawalpindi area. The second objective is to analyze the ground realities about harassment in society. It is very necessary for all of us to know that what is the actual situation in which the transgender people live. How they fulfill their needs and what are the reasons they leave their family and start living with another transgender. The third objective is to give some suggestions and recommendations to overcome/readdress issues. The objectives of this study are:

- Identification of state of transgenders in district Rawalpindi
- Analysis of the state of the transgenders individuals in society
- To suggest some measures and recommendations

METHODOLOGY ADAPTED

LOCALE

The study area was Rawalpindi. The study locale was Rehman Abad.

SAMPLING:

The researchers have used simple random sampling technique. There was difficulty to study all population so, 60 respondents were selected.

The interview method was used to collect all relevant data. Through interview schedule the data was collected. This interview schedule was including different questions with relevant research. Several variables were used for data collecting based on consciousness increase through literature reviews has been done.

PRETESTING:

Interview schedule was pre-tested on 10 respondents throughout a commencement appointment of meadow previous to collecting the real data. As a consequence of pre-testing, a number of new questions were customized and a number of were additional according to supplies to obtain improved reply from the chosen population. In thorough facts compilation in the meadow face to face interviewing was adopted by researcher.

DATA ANALYSIS

Through SPSS the data were analyzed by using frequency distribution and percentage techniques

PERCENTAGE

The response of frequency distribution the following formula was used:

$$P = \frac{f}{N} (100)$$

Where

P= Percentage

F= Absolute frequency

N= Total number of respondents

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

This chapter indicates the study and the debate of the data. The facts were in regular distribution tables. The discussion of finding precedes its respective graphs. Finally, a brief of pertinent study has been presented.

Graph: 1 Distribution of respondents by their age

It was asked from the respondents about their age? A significant number of respondents (32%) replied that their age is below 18, similarly, between 19-30 was (48%), between 31-40 was (20%) and finally between 31-40 were (20%).

Graph 2: Distribution of respondents by their educational status

In this regard when it was asked from the researchers what is their education status? Then researches were shocked to know that about (24%) respondents told that they are illiterate. Crux of these findings the researchers came to know that deprived of education there is difficult to endure. There is dire need for transgenders to build separate schools or sensitize people to equally respect them.

Graph 3: Distribution of respondents by their parent’s support

A vast majority of the respondents (90%) affirms that their families are not supporting them and only (10%) respondents confirmed that their families are supporting them. Living without parents, leads them socio-phyco complications. In this regard government should make new amendments in law to bound parents to not leave transgender people alone.

Graph 4: Distribution of respondents who leave family by their will

A major chunk of (49%) respondents informed that their family leave them alone, similarly very less (11%) respondents told that they leave their family by their own will. In the same veins, equally need for parents to take some responsibility and human respect for their transgenders kids.

Graph 5: Distribution of respondents by humiliate their class fellows

When researcher asked to the respondents that when they go to school then does their class mates humiliate them? Almost (62%) respondents agreed that they were humiliated by the others students. To overcome/readdress maliciously condition of transgenders, there is dire need to sensitize community members, to give respect and safety.

Graph 6: Distribution of respondents by facing harassment in society

When asked do they face harassment in their society, then (39%) of the respondents told that they are facing harassment in society. In this regard, Government, NGOs, and relevant social welfare department can play their vital role to curtail this cruel human discrimination.

INTERVIEW WITH TRANSGENDER'S

Their own wording is described as under,

- *Zamree has a matric degree, she did not find job. She told to the researchers that "there is difficulty to find a job in a good place. Typically, people hesitate to talk and work with us.*
- *Bejili is 30 years old, when I was young almost 6 years old then told me that leave this house. Then I came to my Guru, I happy to live with my guru. My guru is so much loving and caring more than my family. In any stage of my life I do not want to leave him.*
- *Lina has a graduation degree she told that "last year I found job in Rawalpindi but after 1 month they informed me to leave this job without any reason.*
- *Shanza is 23 years old and she is living alone. She was living separate for 21 years. She informed that "when I was 9-year-old parents forced me to leave house because in our surroundings people do not accept transgenders to live with them".*
- *Chimachi was 34 years old living separately for 25 years, she was mentally distressed and while interacting with researcher she was confused and disturbed. She informed that "people do not like to live with us that is why we live separately".*

RECOMMENDATIONS

- It is proposed that, state and society both have to be active in bringing transgenders into the mainstream through opportunities in education and employment.
- Education for all is necessary for individual himself and for the society. There is need to work in this arena to build separate schools for transgenders, so they can learn and participate in country growth.
- For transgender mainstreaming, it is advocated that Govt. should provide vocational, training and technical institutions for capacity building of transgender and for jobs.
- Both, Govt. and NGOs should launch some projects to decrease the drug addictions in transgender. During research, the researchers noticed that they are using drugs also, so there is need to give awareness about drugs.
- Equally important, religious leaders positively represent them in their religious addresses and give them religious education to perform religious rituals.
- Further, the Social Welfare Department needs to emphasis on this community and need to protect their rights, starting with education, health, and social protection.
- More importantly, there is dire need to welcome transgenders of any age and specially the transgender who are elders, requires the modification of existing services, polices and agendas. We should try to make their life easy as to tell them special and respect their feelings.

REFERENCES

- i. *Worlds times (2018) Transgenders' Rights in Pakistan Still a long way to go Available at http://jworldtimes.com/jwt2015/magazine_archives/jwt2017/february2017/transgenders-rights-in-pakistan-still-a-long-way-to-go/ retrieved on 11-02-2018*
- ii. *Dawn 2018, Transgender voting rights, can be accessible at <https://www.dawn.com/news/1389871>*
- iii. *Raza 2017, Transgender Community in Pakistan, available at <http://pakteahouse.net/2017/01/16/transgender-community-in-pakistan/>*
- iv. *Yumna Fiaz (2017) Times of Pakistan, problems faced by transgenders in Pakistan, available at <http://timesofpakistan.pk/opinion/2017-02-02/problems-faced-by-transgender-pakistan/104437/retrived> on 10-02-2018*
- v. *Aurat foundation, a research study Silent No More Transgender Community in Pakistan*
- vi. *Sabrina (2018) Pakistan's transgender community takes another step forward*
- vii. *Mahwish Akhtar (2016), Transgenders problems in Pakistan, News Pakistan available at <https://www.newspakistan.tv/transgender-in-pakistan-by-mahwish-akhtar-jinnah-university-for-women/>, retrieved on 211-2018*

- viii. Murtaza 2017, *Transgender Rights Protection Bill 2017 presented Before The Senate*, available at <https://www.pakistantoday.com.pk/2017/07/10/transgender-rights-protection-bill-2017-presented-before-the-senate/>
- ix. *Human Rights and Transgender People in Pakistan*, international gay and lesbian human rights commission, human rights for everyone everywhere
- x. Samuel (2018) *Independent*, Pakistan passes law guaranteeing transgender rights Law bans discrimination and harassment of transgender people, available at <https://www.independent.co.uk/news/world/asia/pakistan-transgender-rights-lgbt-national-assembly-law-drivers-license-passport-a8343321.html>
- xi. Hamiz 2018, *Pakistan Passes Landmark Transgender Rights Law*, available at <https://propakistani.pk/2018/05/10/pakistan-passes-landmark-transgender-rights-law/>
- xii. Dawn, *transgender rights*, 2018, available at <https://www.dawn.com/news/1350646>
- xiii. Gartner, W. B. (1985). *A Conceptual Framework for describing the phenomenon of new venture creation*. *Academy of Management Review*, 10: 696-706.
- xiv. *International Labour Office (2002a). Decent Work and the Informal Economy*. Geneva: International Labour Office.
- xv. Lazarus Muchabaiwa, *Sex Differentials in Child Survival in Zimbabwe*, *International Journal of Management Sciences and Business Research* 06(2017):25-47
- xvi. Lerner, M. Brush, C. G. & Hisrich, R. D. (2005). *Women-owned businesses: An exploratory study comparing factors affecting performance*. *Journal of Business Venturing*, 12,
- xvii. Beck, T., Levine, R., & Loayza, N. (2000). *Finance and the Sources of Growth*. *Journal of financial economics*, 58(1), 261-300.
- xviii. Calderón, C., & Liu, L. (2003). *The direction of causality between financial development and economic growth*. *Journal of development economics*, 72(1), 321-334.
- xix. Sheikh Farhan Ashraf, Cai Li, Majid Murad, *Impact of Successor's Personality Traits on Small & Medium Enterprise (SME) Family Business Succession*, *International Journal of Management Sciences and Business Research* 12(2017):54-64
- xx. *The Guardian*, Pakistan transgender leader calls for end to culture of 'gurus'.
- xxi. *Interview with Zamree* 3 April, 2018, Rehman Abad, Rawalpindi
- xxii. *Interview with Bejili*, 5 April, 2018 Rehman Abad, Rawalpindi
- xxiii. *Interview with Lina*, 5 April, 2018 Rehman Abad, Rawalpindi
- xxiv. *Interview with Chimachi*, 9 May, 2018 Sadar, Rawalpindi